

Efficacy Outcomes in the Phase 3 COMBI-AD Study of Adjuvant Dabrafenib Plus Trametinib vs Placebo in Patients With Stage III BRAF V600E/K-Mutant Melanoma

Georgina V. Long,¹ Axel Hauschild,² Mario Santinami,³ Victoria Atkinson,⁴ Mario Mandalà,⁵ Vanna Chiarion-Sileni,⁶ James Larkin,⁷ Marta Nyakas,⁸ Caroline Dutriaux,⁹ Andrew Haydon,¹⁰ Caroline Robert,¹¹ Laurent Mortier,¹² Jacob Schachter,¹³ Dirk Schadendorf,¹⁴ Thierry Lesimple,¹⁵ Ruth Plummer,¹⁶ Ran Ji,¹⁷ Pingkuan Zhang,¹⁷ Bijoyesh Mookerjee,¹⁷ Jeff Legos,¹⁷ Richard Kefford,¹⁸ Reinhard Dummer,¹⁹ John M. Kirkwood²⁰

¹Melanoma Institute Australia, The University of Sydney, Royal North Shore and Mater Hospitals, Sydney, NSW, Australia; ²University Hospital Schleswig-Holstein, Kiel, Germany; ³Fondazione Istituto Nazionale Tumori, Milano, Italy; ⁴Princess Alexandra Hospital, Gallipoli Medical Research Foundation, University of Queensland, QLD, Australia; ⁵Papa Giovanni XIII Cancer Center Hospital, Bergamo, Italy; ⁶Melanoma Oncology Unit, Veneto Oncology Institute, Gattamelato, Padova, Italy; ⁷Royal Marsden NHS Foundation Trust, London, United Kingdom; ⁸Oslo University Hospital, Oslo, Norway; ⁹Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Bordeaux, Hôpital Saint-André, Bordeaux, France; ¹⁰The Alfred Hospital, Melbourne, VIC, Australia; ¹¹Institut Gustave Roussy, Paris, France; ¹²Université de Lille, INSERM U 1189, CHRU Lille, France; ¹³Ella Institute for Melanoma, Sheba Medical Center, Tel Hashomer, Israel; ¹⁴University Hospital Essen, Essen, Germany, and German Cancer Consortium, Heidelberg, Germany; ¹⁵Medical Oncology Department, Centre Eugène Marquis, Rennes, France; ¹⁶Northern Centre for Cancer Care, Freeman Hospital, Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom; ¹⁷Novartis Pharmaceuticals Corporation, East Hanover, NJ, United States; ¹⁸Macquarie University, Melanoma Institute Australia, Westmead Hospital, and University of Sydney, NSW, Australia; ¹⁹University Hospital Zürich Skin Cancer Center, Zürich, Switzerland; ²⁰Melanoma Program, Hillman UPMC Cancer Center, University of Pittsburgh, Pittsburgh, PA, United States

Introduction

- Surgery alone is often curative for patients with localized melanoma; however, those with regional involvement (stage III disease) are at a higher risk for disease progression even with complete surgical resection.^{1,2}
- In phase 3 trials involving patients with previously untreated advanced or metastatic BRAF V600-mutant melanoma, dabrafenib plus trametinib combination therapy improved clinical outcomes and was well tolerated.^{3,4}
- The COMBI-AD study (NCT01682083) is a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 3 trial that evaluated the efficacy and safety of dabrafenib plus trametinib combination therapy in patients with completely resected, high-risk, stage III, BRAF V600E/K-mutant melanoma without prior anticancer therapy.⁵

Figure 1. Study Rationale^{3,5-8}

MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; mut, mutated; pERK, phosphorylated extracellular signal-regulated kinase.

Figure 2. Study Design

BID, twice daily; DMFS, distant metastasis-free survival; ECOG, Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group; FFR, freedom from relapse; OS, overall survival; QD, once daily; RFS, relapse-free survival. ¹Or until disease recurrence, death, unacceptable toxicity, or withdrawal of consent. ²Patients were followed for disease recurrence until the first recurrence and thereafter for survival. ³The study will be considered complete and final OS analysis will occur when = 70% of randomized patients have died or are lost to follow-up. ⁴Study was designed to provide > 90% power (assuming = 410 RFS events observed) to detect an HR of 0.71 with an overall 2-sided type I error rate of 5%. New primary melanoma considered as an event. ⁵OS was to be tested only if the primary endpoint (RFS) significantly favoured the combination arm.

Figure 3. Primary Analysis: RFS and OS

Median follow-up: 2.8 years

Data cutoff: 30 June 2017. NR, not reached. ¹Pre-specified significance boundary (P = 0.00019); next interim analysis planned when 50% of events have occurred.

Figure 4. Primary Analysis: RFS by Subgroup

Data cutoff: 30 June 2017.

Figure 5. RFS: Stage IIIA

NR, not reached.

Figure 6. RFS: Stage IIIB

NR, not reached.

Figure 7. RFS: Stage IIC

NR, not reached.

Figure 8. RFS: Stage IIIB and IIC

NR, not reached.

Figure 9. RFS: Micrometastases

NR, not reached.

Figure 10. RFS: Macrometastases

NR, not reached.

Figure 11. RFS: Without Primary Tumour Ulceration

NR, not reached.

Figure 12. RFS: With Primary Tumour Ulceration

NR, not reached.

Table 1. Type of Recurrence at First Recurrence

Type of recurrence, n (%)	Dabrafenib Plus Trametinib (n = 166)	Placebo (n = 248)
Distant recurrence	103 (62)	133 (54)
Local/regional recurrence	61 (37)	114 (46)
Secondary primary melanoma	7 (4)	8 (3)
Death	3 (2)	1 (< 1)

Table 2. Primary Analysis: Safety Summary

AE Category, n (%)	Dabrafenib Plus Trametinib (n = 435)	Placebo (n = 432)
Any AE	422 (97)	380 (88)
AEs related to study treatment	398 (91)	272 (63)
Grade 3/4 AEs related to study treatment	136 (31)	21 (5)
Any SAE	155 (36)	44 (10)
SAEs related to study treatment	117 (27)	17 (4)
AEs leading to dose interruption	289 (66)	65 (15)
AEs leading to dose reduction	167 (38)	11 (3)
AEs leading to treatment discontinuation ^a	114 (26)	12 (3)
Fatal AEs related to study drug	0	0

AE, adverse event; SAE, serious adverse event. ^aMost common AEs leading to treatment discontinuation in the dabrafenib plus trametinib arm were pyrexia (9%) and chills (4%).

- Most common AEs in the dabrafenib plus trametinib arm were pyrexia (63%) and fatigue (47%)

Table 3. Characterisation of Pyrexia Events

	Dabrafenib Plus Trametinib (n = 435)	Placebo (n = 432)
Patients with pyrexia events, n (%)	292 (67)	66 (15)
Median time to onset of first pyrexia occurrence (range), days	23 (1-28)	53 (1-373)
Median duration of pyrexia (range), days	3 (1-92)	3 (1-340)
Pyrexia event characteristics, n (%) ^a		
Serious adverse event	71 (24)	4 (6)
Grade 3	24 (8)	2 (3)
Grade 4	1 (< 1)	0
Number of pyrexia occurrences, n (%) ^a		
1	83 (28)	45 (68)
2	57 (20)	11 (17)
≥ 3	152 (52)	10 (15)

^aPercentage based on number of patients with pyrexia.

Table 4. Pyrexia Management and Outcome

	Dabrafenib Plus Trametinib (n = 435)	Placebo (n = 432)
Action taken with dabrafenib/trametinib, n (%) ^a		
Drug withdrawn	40 (14)/27 (9)	—
Dose reduced	86 (29)/18 (6)	—
Drug interrupted	202 (69)/121 (41)	—
Recovered/resolved, n (%) ^a	289 (99)	64 (97)

^aPercentage based on number of patients with pyrexia.

Table 5. Secondary Malignancies^a

	Dabrafenib Plus Trametinib (n = 435)	Placebo (n = 432)
New primary melanoma	11 (3)	10 (2)
New cUSCC or keratoacanthoma	8 (2)	7 (2)
New basal cell carcinoma	19 (4)	14 (3)
New nonskin malignancies	10 (2)	4 (1)

cUSCC, cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma; NOS, not otherwise specified. ^aIncludes events occurring after randomisation. Data presented as n (%).

Conclusions

- Dabrafenib plus trametinib reduced the risk of disease recurrence vs placebo in patients with resected stage III, BRAF V600E/K-mutant melanoma; this result was statistically significant and clinically meaningful – RFS HR, 0.47 (95% CI, 0.39-0.58; P < .001) – OS HR, 0.57 (95% CI, 0.42-0.79, P = .0006 [pre-specified significance boundary, P = .00019])
- RFS benefit was observed in all patient subgroups – Stage IIIA HR, 0.44; stage IIIB HR, 0.50; stage IIC HR, 0.45 – Micrometastases HR, 0.44; macrometastases HR, 0.43 – Nonulcerated HR, 0.49; ulcerated HR, 0.46
- Although pyrexia was the most common AE, it was well characterised and manageable
- Dabrafenib plus trametinib represents a significant advance for the adjuvant treatment of stage III BRAF V600-mutant melanoma

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